

Yeasts Associated with Spoilage of Some Selected Fruits in Sokoto Metropolis

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to determine the involvement of yeasts in fruit spoilage. Pour plate method by serial dilution was used for the isolation of the yeast isolates. A total of six genera of yeasts were recovered from the rotten fruit samples. They include *Geotrichum sp.*, *Saccharomyces sp.*, *Schizosaccharomyces sp.*, *Nematospora sp.*, *Kloeckera sp.* and *Hanseniospora sp.* The highest frequency of occurrence was obtained in *Geotrichum sp.* followed by *Saccharomyces sp.* and least frequency of occurrence was recorded by *Hanseniospora* and *Kloeckera* spp. It would be recommended that proper handling of fruits, adequate sanitary measures and sorting of rotten fruits should be employed to reduce the incidence of yeast rots of fruits.

Keyword: Yeasts, spoilage, fruits, Sokoto Metropolis.

INTRODUCTION

Fruit is a fertilized and ripened ovary. Fruits supply vitamins, minerals, sugars, organic acids and dietary fibre [1]. Fruits are used to make soft drinks, sauce and curing of diseases [2,3].

Fruits are prone to postharvest deterioration caused by microorganisms. It was estimated that about 20% of all fruits and vegetables produced is lost each year due to spoilage [4]. Post harvest rots occurred due to activities of fungi (Yeasts and moulds), bacteria, viruses and nematodes. Postharvest spoilage of fruits is mainly caused by fungi. Yeasts are saprophytes growing on substrates containing sugar such as fruits, grains, vegetables, exudates from trees and nectar of flowers [5]. The following yeasts *kloeckera apiculata*, *Candida guilliermondi*, *Candida stellata*, *Pichia kluyveri*, *P. membranaefaciens* and *Geotrichum candidum* were isolated from rotted orange, lime, mandrins and grape fruits [6]. Also [7] and Mbajiaka and [8] reported *Geotrichum candidum*, *Geotrichum sp.*, *Saccharomyces sp.* and *Candida tropicalis* from rotten tomato and pawpaw fruits.

However, there is scarcity of information on yeasts associated with spoilage of fruits and vegetables. The aim of this paper is to isolate and identify yeasts associated with spoilage of orange, tomato, mango, pepper and banana fruits in Sokoto metropolis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection of samples

A total of 100 rotten (tomato, orange, pepper, banana, mango) fruit samples were randomly selected from five different markets; Sokoto central market, Gawon nama, Bado, Mabera and Nagarta located in Sokoto metropolis. Twenty five (25) fruits were collected for each fruit type. The fruits were put singly into sterile polythene bags and transferred to laboratory for analysis.

Isolation and identification of the yeasts

The yeasts were isolated using pour plate method by serial dilution. Rotten fruits were washed with sterile distilled water and surface sterilized with 70% ethanol solution. The fruit samples were crushed in sterile mortar and pestle and serially diluted using sterile distilled water. The dilution of 10^{-5} was used for plating. Aliquots of 1ml of each sample supernatant were transferred into sterile petri dishes and 15ml of nutrient yeast dextrose agar (NYDA) medium was poured. The set up was incubated at room temperature for 72 hours. Representative yeast colonies were selected and subcultured on NYDA medium to obtain pure cultures. The yeast isolates were identified based on their colonial and microscopic features. The identification was carried out by reference to [9].

Pathogenicity test

Healthy fruits were washed with tap water and surface sterilized with 70% ethanol solution. With help of sterile scalpel wounds were created on the fruits. Mycelial discs were lifted from cultures of the different isolates and introduced directly into wounded tissues. Four fruits were inoculated for each isolate and fruit type. Ten fruits wounded with sterile needle but not inoculated served as control. The treated fruits were incubated at room temperature for 72 hours. At the end of the incubation period the fruits were observed for symptoms of rots. The causal agents were reisolated from the infected fruits and compared with original isolates.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Six genera of yeasts have been isolated from the five types of fruit samples. These include *Geotrichum sp.*, *Saccharomyces sp.*, *Nematospora sp.*, *Schizosaccharomyces sp.*, *Hanseniospora sp.* and *Kloeckera sp.* The highest frequency of occurrence was observed in *Geotrichum sp.* followed by *Saccharomyces sp.* and

Yeast isolates	Frequency of occurrence (%)
<i>Geotrichum sp.</i>	33.3
<i>Saccharomyces sp.</i>	26.7
<i>Nematospora sp.</i>	13.3
<i>Schizosaccharomyces sp.</i>	13.3
<i>Hanseniospora sp.</i>	6.7
<i>Kloeckera sp.</i>	6.7

the least was recorded by *Hanseniospora* and *Kloeckera species*.

The results were presented in table 1.

The results of pathogenicity test confirmed that all the yeast isolates were pathogenic on the fruits. The pathogens produced different symptoms of rots which are similar to the original ones. This indicated that all the yeasts isolates were involved in the spoilage of the fruits.

It was clear that there was variation in yeasts genera with fruit type. This may be attributed to the variation in chemical compositions of the fruits. *Saccharomyces*, *Kloeckera*, *Geotrichum* and *Nematospora* were the yeast genera that caused rotting of orange, tomato and mango fruits respectively. These fruits were regarded as acidic fruits. While pepper which was known to be a spice was infected by *Saccharomyces sp.* and *Schizosaccharomyces sp.* The rotting of banana which was taken to be a neutral fruit was caused by species of *Hanseniospora* and *Schizosaccharomyces*. The results were shown in table 2

Table 2: Incidence of yeasts associated with spoilage of fruits in Sokoto metropolis.

Yeasts isolates	Fruit type				
	Tomato	Pepper	Orange	Mango	Banana
<i>Geotrichum sp.</i>	4	-	3	2	1
<i>Saccharomyces sp.</i>	-	2	2	4	-
<i>Schizosaccharomyces sp.</i>	-	2	-	-	2
<i>Nematospora sp.</i>	4	-	-	-	-
<i>Kloeckera sp.</i>	2	-	-	-	-
<i>Hanseniospora sp.</i>	-	-	-	-	2

This indicated that chemical compositions of certain fruits might have allowed the growth of some yeasts genera and inhibited the growth of the others. The growth of these microorganisms is relatively attributed to the pH values of the fruit samples. Generally, the growth of these yeasts is mostly favour by the acidic and sugary nature of these fruits.

In this study *Nematospora sp.* and *Geotrichum sp.* were found to be responsible for the rots of tomato fruits. Similarly, *Nematospora sp.*, *Geotrichum sp.*, *Geotrichum candidum*, *Candida tropicalis* and *Trichoderma sp.* were isolated from rotted tomato fruits [7,10,11,12,13,14]. *Saccharomyces species* were described as brewer yeasts involved in the fermentation of many agricultural commodities such as millet, guinea corn, potato to make beer. But these types of yeasts were among the others identified to be causing rotting of fruits in Sokoto metropolis. This is in agreement with findings of [8] and [10] who reported *Saccharomyces sp.*, *Cryptococcus sp.* and *Candida species* to be causing spoilage of pepper, orange and tomato fruits. Yeasts belonging to the genera *Schizosaccharomyces*, *Hanseniospora* and *Kloeckera* were discovered by [15] Spencer [6] and [16] to be occurring on orange, lime, grape fruit, plums and mandrins. These yeasts were also found to be causing fruits rots in Sokoto.

From the results obtained, it could be deduce that yeasts caused serious spoilage of fruits in Sokoto. The rotting of the fruits usually occurred as a result of growing conditions in the field, handling during harvest, transit and storage conditions. Injuries to the fruits during any of the above processes were important factors for high incidence of fruit rots.

The occurrence of these microorganisms in fruits is an unavoidable circumstance. But authentic measures could be taken to minimize the destructive effects of these microorganisms in fruits. Some of these measures include :

- ❖ Proper handling of fruits during harvest, transit and storage.
- ❖ Proper sanitary measures are absolutely essential to reduce rot diseases of fruits
- ❖ Injuries to the fruits should be avoided
- ❖ Fumigation of stores to reduce yeast infection
- ❖ Sorting of rotten fruits will also reduce infection.

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